

MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS INFLUENCING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN OLDER ADULTS: A REVIEW

Elton Fernando Ferreira de Souza Vieira^{1*}, João Victor Rodrigues de Oliveira Lima¹,
Cláudia Maria Goulart¹, Raphael Lopes Olegário^{1,2}

¹Faculty of Physical Education, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil.

²Faculty of Medicine, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil.

*e-mail: eltonsozafef@gmail.com

Introduction: The populational number of older adults is rising dramatically in Brazil, based on the concept of the World Health Organization, which considers a person to be elderly at 60 years of age or older if residing in a developing country. Research into physical activity behaviors has been conducted from several different theoretical perspectives (e.g., self-determination theory). Integrating the constructs of theories may improve our understanding of factors that motivate older adults to participate in physical fitness activities. **Aim:** This review aims to identify older adults' motivating factors for the practice of physical fitness activities. **Methods:** Publications up to October 2009 were identified by searching the electronic databases: Scientific Electronic Library Online and Virtual Health Library. In addition, data was found in the repositories Google Scholar and ResearchGate. The criterion for inclusion was studies published in Portuguese or English, carried out with Brazilian older adults, individuals aged ≥ 60 , older adults' practitioners who are beginners or regular practitioners of physical fitness activities, and using the Regular Practice of Physical and Sports Activity Inventory (IMPRAFE) questionnaire as an instrument for data collection about the motivational factors. **Results:** The electronic search retrieved $\Sigma n = 18$ studies, of which $\Sigma n = 9$ were excluded after screening by full-text reading. For the final analysis, $\Sigma n = 9$ studies were included in the qualitative synthesis. The results of our investigation revealed that the main motivational factors for Brazilian older adults to practice physical fitness activities are health, sociability, pleasure, and stress control. **Discussion:** The behaviors regulated by the factors health, sociability, and stress control are more self-determined compared to the motivational factors aesthetics and competitiveness, also evaluated by IMPRAFE. The regulatory style of motivation is related to the attitudes and objectives that trigger the action (i.e., the reason for the action). **Conclusion:** Knowing the motivational factors that lead older adults to perform physical activity becomes extremely important for the practice of physical education professionals, as it can enable adaptation in relation to students' expectations, increasing satisfaction and permanence.

Keywords: physical activity; motivation; aging; sport psychology; health

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